

Management

THE IMPACTS OF THE SPECIAL REGIONAL POLICY TO THE LOCAL GOVERNMENT ENFORCEMENT IN SOUTHERN THAILAND (CASE STUDY AT THE REPEL DISTRICT, KRONGPINANG, THAILAND)

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Abstract

Special territory policy has been using in the Southern Thailand is a central government's policy (Bangkok) in terms of giving absolute authority to the military, to resolve the conflicts in southern Thailand. The policy includes three matters: 1) Martial law of 2547 (the regulations in state of emergency in the 2004); 2) the Emergency Decree 2548 PO-Ro-Ko (Security rules in state of emergency); 3) Internal Security Act in the 2551 PO – RO – BO (the rule in terms of internal security implementation of 2008). This paper aimed to analyzing the impacts of special regional policies on local governance in southern Thailand (case study in Repel district, Krongpinang, Thailand. This research used descriptive qualitative methodology. based on research results, can be concluded that the impacts of the implementation of special regional policy; 1) the functional disappearance of local government; 2) local government was depressed by military system; 3) society harmonization to local government (village head) decreased.

Keywords: Patani; Conflict; Special Regional Policy.

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1. Introduction

Thailand is a royal state was located in southeast Asia. Thailand or *Muang Thai* was known generally, its name take from the name of the tribes in the country of the Thai tribe. In the history, this Thai tribe was always called by Europa people with the name "Siam".

Thailand is a royal state that still thick with the monarchy constitution system to governance the country or in another name was known as "*The White Elephant country*" and Thailand is the only country that was never officially colonized by the colonial state. How Thailand escaped from the colonial state at that time while the position of the Thai state as a bridge of the country's vast land to an archipelago to like Malaysia, Indonesia and others. Apparently, there is a landmark that

became a fort that is a dividing the area of the colonial state controlled, between the government of Thailand and British with an engagement namely “Anglo *Treaty in 1909s*”. in the Malay land known as PATANI.

The Anglo Treaty is an agreement that divided the territory of Thailand ‘s regional to others countries (colonial state) which divides by measurement through a river called the Sungai Kholok river. The Anglo treaty brought out Kedah, Pelis, Teranggau and Kelantan were handed over by The British. Whilst, Patani region remained in the Siames authority. In deeds, this agreement is not approved by the Patani people itself (Malek, 1994:236).

After the end of the Word War II, British gave back the independence to every nation that was took place by it. Automatically, after giving back the rights to those nation in its area, they affiliated and builded a Malay state namely Malaysia, whilst the Patani region ramians under the Thai government (Tuwaemaegae, 2014:29-30). The Patani is a region that quite large enough. Therefore, the Thai government then divided into three provinces, namely: Yala, Pattani, and Narathiwat and parts of Songkla district. The purpose of this policy implementation is to be easy to set and organize the policy to practice it in the country.

After the division of territory between Siam and British, the separatist movement is widespread and increasing. Furthermore, the emerged of Mahmud Mahyidin or was known as the tiger of Malaya. Mahmud Mahyidin is the last king’s descendants of Patani kingdom. He was a leader of the movement a budging in the internal and external. And deal with the British to improve the Patani Malay people. It is important to regain Malay sovereignty.

According to Eko (2003:5) the government has three main functions that must be implemented, namely the function of community services, development functions and protection functions. The most important of these three functions related to the resolution of the conflict in southern Thailand. The government role to service its people in the region to fulfill the needs and accommodate the asymmetry. The function of development to improve stability in society. The function of protection if the condition of society is in chaos the duty of the government must take care of the society.

After the government inaugurated this regional policy that giving the full authority the the military to cope with the widespread conflict in the southern Thailand. 3 types of rules that have been using in this special regional: 1) Martial law of 2547 (the regulations in state of emergency in the 2004); 2) the Emergency Decree 2548 *PO-Ro-Ko* (Security rules in state of emergency); 3) Internal Security Act in the 2551 *PO – RO – BO* (the rule in terms of internal security implementation of 2008).

Martial law of 2547 (the regulations in state of emergency in the 2004) article 15 twit, the military is entitled to arrest anyone who becomes enemy or who violate this regulation, the military has the right to capture in accordance with the needs of the military within 7 days. Apparently, this role is giving the absolute authority to the military in order to overcome the conflict as maximum as possible and the stability in society.

The Emergency Decree 2548 (2005) *PO-Ro-Ko* (Security rules in state of emergency) article 17, this regulation provided both of the local government and the military do not to take responsibility of every single acts of eradication of conflicts and to secure the state if it is in accordance with responsibilities. When in a government-controlled military environment, the government always focusing on state security only. This such acted will spread to another things or problems, for instance, the emerge of narcotic or stealing problems that getting increased every single day. This is because the police agencies are also under the military authority.

This special regional policy has gave full control to the military. Automatically, the local government agencies itself could not work with full authority in order to keep the stability in its society and largely has become the victims of this role. In the Thailand constitution about the regional regulation No. 2 article 28, 2510 when the local people unsatisfied with something have to complain the problem to the head of the village. Due to the village head is who have to take full of responsible in its local.

One of the villages with relatively high military intervention was the village of Repel located in Tambon Krogpinang, whereas prior to the 2004-armed conflict, Repel's village had a higher quality of human resources than other village human resources, the proof of Repel village produced many teachers and high-ranking officials in government. but after 2004, improvements and developments in Repel village declined. Accordance to the views of Makpakri Lateh (*Repel village head*) namely:

“Before the military has intervened into the village, I have full authority in carry out any activity within the village. But after the special regional policy was used and then my authority was undertaken by the military. I have to submit every activity to the military and wait for approval of it”.

This indicate that when the government implementing a special regional regulation would affected to the authority of the village head in generating stability in his village than in the past. Makpakri Lateh was the village head appointed to the village head prior to 2004. Makpakri Lateh has been the village head of the Repel before the implementing of the special regional policy in the village till nowadays. This research emerged to provide the village head himself to compare the differential of before and after the using of the policy into the Repel village. Moreover, analyzer myself from the Repel village also. this study is also more in-depth what will be research, because researcher can approach directly with the environment and government officials at the village level, analyzer can interview and seek information maximally to get the accurate data. Based on the explanation of the background above, analyzer will research with the title “*Analysis the impacts of the special regional policy to the local government enforcement in southern Thailand*”.

2. Materials and Methods

Special Performance

Martial law of 2004 article 2 “when there is a need to maintain the security and stability of the State even if the problem arises from outside or within its own country, this rule shall replace the laws or regulations in that area”.

After the separatist movement began to take up arms and attacked the military camps located in Narathiwat in 2004. this attack for the government's own view is very dangerous to society in general, hence the government must be forced to use emergency rule in order to keep the security of society and country. Accordingly, the government set the policy up in three matters; 1) Martial law of 2547 (the regulations in state of emergency in the 2004); 2) the Emergency Decree 2548 *PO-Ro-Ko* (Security rules in state of emergency) ; 3) Internal Security Act in the 2551 *PO – RO – BO* (the rule in terms of internal security implementation of 2008). Those three regulations are called the special territory that is a special rule used in certain circumstances.

- 1) พระราชบัญญัติกฎอัยการศึก พ.ศ. 2547 (Martial law of 2004; The Regulations In State Of Emergency)

กฎอัยการศึก in the Thai language dictionary of 2554 are government regulations and powers granted to the military in order for the military to have full authority to address or maintain the security of the state through a special judicial institution for the military so that the military can maximize its security duties (Thai Dictionary 2012).

This policy is not the first time emerged in Thailand, because if there is discrimination within the country, ordinary rules or laws could not cope with the need for special regulations given to the military so that the military can overcome the conditions of the conflict.

This Special territory policy by using special regulation to give full authority to the military, this is not the first time in Thailand adapted this, but for several times and succeed always. When the condition returning to normal, these rules must be abolished. Due to the regulation will results to the human right and the democracy system. Yet in the Patani regional, thses regulation has continued for 14 years however, the conditions in patani are getting worse and the damage is widespread.

- 2) พระราชกำหนดการบริหารราชการในสถานการณ์ พ.ศ .2548 (The Emergency Decree 2005 *PO-Ro-Ko*; Security rules in state of emergency)

พระราชกำหนดการบริหารราชการในสถานการณ์ พ.ศ .2548 or largely called *PO – RO – KO* is a policy from the prime minister to cope with the conflict or war or civil war within the country, with the intention of carried out in accordance with what is desired by the government, and only done temporarily in 3 months only. And only done temporarily that is 3 months only. If the state of conflict or war has not finished to be extended again until the government feel the situation in the society is safe and has returned to normal circumstances then the government must pull return the rules and use ordinary laws and regulations. This Po Ro Ko Regulation is valid for 3 months only, but it can be extended without limits, when it is approved by the Thai government. this policy can extend until the government feels the country is in a safety state.

The local government also get involved the action of military. Due to the military itself need them when the military want to use the policy. The military have to get of approval of three government agencies before using that rule within the district; 1. The police, the local government (governor or regent) and the military themselves. This regulation more flexible than *the Martial Law*. However, the authority of this law is higher than the Martial law.

- 3) พระราชบัญญัติการรักษาความมั่นคงภายในราชอาณาจักรพุทธศักราช 2551 (2008), *Po Ro Bo* (Internal Security Act; the rule in terms of internal security implementation)

If the government feels that the chaos that occurs in every region of Thailand is out of the capability to reconcile with ordinary rules, the prime minister has the right to make a policy to deal with the situation. The regimented arrangements will be handed over to the military chief to act maximally, so that the central government feels the state is back in a safe state, but it is lighter than the previous regulation of emergency and security regulations, which prohibits people from demonstrating and the military must be held accountable for all its actions only if the military needs to operate where it does not have to be approved such as the regulation of Po Ro Ko (Kapook, 2010).

In The PO-RO-BO regulation, the Thai government has established an agency, known as *Ko Or Ro Mo No* กองอำนวยการรักษาความมั่นคงภายในราชอาณาจักร) กอ.รมน(.. directly, this institution gets instruction from the prime minister, that is why the military under this institution is higher than ordinary military power.

The Local Government in Thailand

According to the Thailand constitution, 2534 B. (1991). The local government is divided into two; Changwat (province) and Impor (district).

According to Wahjosumidjo (2007) leadership indicators are listed as follows:

- 1) Being fair: in the activities of an organization, a sense of togetherness among members is a must. Togetherness is a reflection of an essential agreement between employees and a leader in achieving organizational goals.
- 2) Suggestion: suggestion is an influence that can move the hearts of others. It is very important in maintaining and nurturing self-esteem and a sense of dedication, participation, and a sense of togetherness among employees.
- 3) Supporting objectives: the achievement of organizational goals is not automatically established, but it must be supported by leadership.
- 4) The catalyst: a leader acts as a catalyst. The leader always improves all existing human resources and raises the motivation.
- 5) Creating a sense of security: every leader is able to create a sense of security for his/her employee. Leaders must be able to maintain the positive feeling and optimism in order that the employee is able to face all problems, do duties well, and feel safe.
- 6) As the representative of the organization: a leader has an important role in all aspects of an organization. It means that the leader is a role model for the employee in terms of attitude and Excellency.
- 7) The source of inspiration: a leader must always be able to motivate the employee to achieve the goals of the organization by performing job effectively and efficiently.
- 8) Respectful: award is a gift for those who perform excellent performance. A leader is able to award the employee to motivate the employee in order that they can increase the job performance.

Job Satisfaction

Satisfaction is a psychological atmosphere about pleasant or unpleasant feelings about their work (Davis, Keith, 2001). Meanwhile Porter and Lawler in Bavendam (2000) explained that job

satisfaction is an undimensional building, where a person has a general satisfaction or dissatisfaction with his work. Vroom as cited by Ahmad, MA Roshidi (1999) defines job satisfaction as a reference of an employee's effective orientation to their role in the current position he holds.

Indicators of job satisfaction according to Hasibuan (2009) cover six measurements, namely:

- 1) Fair and decent
- 2) Appropriate communication services
- 3) The duties
- 4) Atmosphere of work environment.
- 5) Tools that support the work performance
- 6) Leadership and attitude.

Organizational Commitment

According to Wijono (2008), commitment is the determination to do something. A good commitment is a commitment that begins with the leadership. Meanwhile, according to Robbins (2001), an employee's commitment to an organization is a situation in which employees commits to one particular organization and its goals and intend to maintain its membership in the organization.

Allen and Meyer (1990) classify organizational commitment into three dimensions, namely:

- 1) Affective commitment (*affective commitment*) is the emotional involvement of workers to the organization. This commitment is influenced and / or developed when engagement in the organization proves to be a rewarding experience.
- 2) Continuous commitment (*continuance commitment*) is commitment involvement based on the costs incurred due to the release of workers from the organization. This commitment is influenced and / or developed when individuals invest.
- 3) Normative commitment (*normative commitment*) is the involvement of the workers feeling towards the tasks that exist in the organization. Normative commitment is influenced and / or developed as a result of the internalization of normative pressure to perform certain actions, and receives benefits that generate feelings of obligations to be reciprocated.

Conceptual Framework

Based on the above description, then the researcher compiled a framework of theoretical thinking that states the influence between the variables in this study. For the details, the theoretical framework is illustrated in the image below:

Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

The researcher formulated hypothesis so that the researcher is able to conduct a research and discuss problem in this research very well. According to Sutrisno Hadi (1993), the hypothesis is a statement or temporary conclusion while the researcher figures out the final conclusion of the research. The hypotheses of this research are:

- 1) H1: Leadership affects employee performance
- 2) H2: Job satisfaction affects employee performance
- 3) H3: Organizational affects employee performance

Method

Population and Sample

Population

Population is amount of all objects (units / individuals) whose characteristics are examined (Djarwanto and Pengestu, 1998). The population in this study was 295 employees at RSUD Besuki, Situbondo, Indonesia.

Sample

Sample, according to Indriantoro and Supomo (2004) is defined as part of the populations that will be studied, used to infer or describe the entire population. Selection of samples with appropriate methods can accurately describe actual population conditions and save research costs effectively. To determine the sample used in this study, the researchers applied following Slovin formula:

$$n = N / (1 + N e^2)$$

$$= 295 / (1 + 295 \times 0.052) = 169.78 \text{ H } 170 \text{ respondents}$$

Next how the selection of samples with random sampling technique based on the probability of each grouping based on the labor type in the hospital with the calculation as seen in table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Number of Respondents by Type of Labor at RSUD (Public Hospital) Besuki Situbondo, Indonesia

No.	Types of	Population Population	Counts	Sample Number
1	Medical / Doctor	11	$\frac{11}{295} \times 170$	6.3 = 6
2	Paramedics (Nurses and midwives)	136	$\frac{136}{295} \times 170$	78.4 = 79
3	Medical support	19	$\frac{19}{295} \times 170$	10.9 = 11
4	Non medical	129	$\frac{129}{295} \times 170$	74.3 = 74
	Total	295		170

Source: Primary Data, 2017

Analysis and Data Processing

After data had been collected, the data is processed and analyzed to answer research questions in order to uncover certain social phenomena. Data analysis is the process of simplifying the data into a form that is easier to read and implement. The method chosen to analyze the data must be in accordance with the research pattern and the variables of the study. Accordingly, this research applied multiple linear regression analysis.

Multiple linear regression analysis is a linear relationship between two or more independent variables (X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n) with the dependent variable (Y). This analysis is to know the direction of the relationship between independent variables and dependent variable whether each independent variable is positive or negative and to predict the value of the dependent variable whether the value of the independent variable increases or decreases.

This study analyzes the relationship of three independent variables and the dependent variable namely leadership variable (X_1), job satisfaction variables (X_2) and organizational commitment variable (X_3) to variable employee performance (Y).

Classic Assumption Test

Assumption test of the regression model is used to know whether the regression model is a good regression model or not (Ghozali, 2016). The classical assumption test conducted in this study is multicollinearity test, heteroscedasticity test, and normality test.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression analysis is used to determine how much influence the relationship of leadership variable (X_1), job satisfaction (x_2), organizational commitment (X_3), the dependent variable employee performance (Y).

The regression equation in this study is:

$$Y = \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + e$$

Description:

Y = Employee Performance

β_1 = Regression coefficient of variable X_1 (Leadership)

X_1 = Leadership

β_2 = Regression coefficient of variable X_2 (Job satisfaction)

X_2 = Job satisfaction

β_3 = Regression coefficient of variable X_3 (Organizational commitment)

X_3 = Organizational commitment

e = Standard error

3. Results and Discussions

Classical Assumption Test

Ghozali (2016), the classical assumption test is useful to know whether or not the deviation of classical assumption to the multiple linear regression equation used. The classical assumption test used in this research was normality test, multicollinearity test and heteroscedasticity test.

Normality Test

The test is used to identify whether residual variable in the model has a normal distribution. Ghozali (2016). Normality test conducted in this research was *Kolmogorov-Smirnov* model testing. According to Sujarweni (2015), states that data is classified as normal if the value of significance > 0.05 . The results of the normality test of this study can be seen in Table 4.3

Table 4.3: The Result of Normality Test

Variable	Significance Value Kolmogorov-Smirnov	Description
Leadership (X1)	0.200	Normal
Job Satisfaction (X2)	0.054	Normal
Commitment (X3)	0.064	Normal
Performance (X4)	0.055	Normal

Source: Primary data, 2018

Based on Table 4.3 it can be seen that all the data on the variables in this study are normally distributed because the whole value of *Kolmogorov-Smirnov* is more than 0.05. It concludes that all data variables are normally distributed.

Multicollinearity Test

This test is to determine independent variables that have similarities with other independent variables in one model. Multicollinearity detection in a model can be seen from the value of *variance inflation factor* (VIF) and *value tolerance*. If the value of *variance inflation factor* (VIF) is not more than 10 and the value of *tolerance* is not less than 0.1, then it can be said that it is free from multicollinearity (Ghozali, 2016). The results of the test multikolinieritas can be seen in Table 4.4

Table 4.4: The Results of Multicollinearity Test

Variable	Value Tolerance	Value VIF	Description
Leadership (X1)	0.351	2.848	Non multicoloniaritas
Job Satisfaction (X2)	0.511	1.957	Non multicoloniaritas
Organizational Commitment (X3)	0.506	1.976	Non multicoloniaritas

Source: Primary Data, 2018

Multicollinearity test results show that all variables have *tolerance* value > 0.1 and VIF value < 10 . Accordingly, it concludes that there is no correlation between independent variables. In other words, all the variables are free from multicollinearity.

Heteroscedasticity Test

The test is to test existence of variant inequality of the residual of another observation in a regression model - a good regression model should be free of heteroscedasticity problem. Sujarweni (2015) stated that a good regression model is free of heteroscedasticity with a significance value greater than 0.05. The result of heteroscedasticity test can be seen in Table 4.5.

Table 4.5: The Results of Heteroscedasticity Test

Variable	Significance Values
Leadership(X1)	0.802
Job Satisfaction (X2)	0.583
Organizational Commitment (X3)	0.401

Source: Primary data, 2018

Based on Table 4.5 heteroscedasticity test results indicate that all variables have a significance value greater than 0, 05. It means that the regression model is free from heteroscedasticity.

Multiple Linear Regression Test

Linear regression is a test that is used to analyze the effect of independent variables (Leadership, Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment) on the dependent variable that is Employee Performance employee of RSUD Besuki, Situbondo, Indonesia. The results of multiple linear regression test in this study can be seen in Table 4.6.

Table 4.6: The Results of Multiple Linear Regression

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	
	B	Std. Error
(constant)	4.426	1.667
Leadership (X1)	0.209	0.019
Job Satisfaction (X2)	0,523	0,035
Organizational Commitment (X3)	-0.044	0.050

Source: Primary data, 2018

Based on the table, the multiple linear regression equation are as follows:

$$Y = 4,426 + 0,209X_1 + 0,523 X_2 - 0,044X_3 + e$$

Description:

- Y = Performance
- X₁ = Leadership
- X₂ = Job Satisfaction
- X₃ = Organizational Commitment

The descriptions of the regression equation in Table 4.6 are explained as follows:

- 1) Constant value 4,426 means that if (X₁, X₂, and X₃) is assumed to be fixed or 0, then Performance value will be 4,426.
- 2) Regression coefficient X₁ (Price) from multiple linear calculation was from coefficient value 0,209. If Leadership increases by one unit, then Performance will increase by 0.209. Coefficient of positive value (+) means that there is a positive relationship between Leadership variables (X₁) and Performance variable (Y). With error standard of 0,019 - it means error rate of Leadership variable that predict Performance is 0,019.
- 3) Regression coefficient X₂ (Job Satisfaction) from multiple linear calculation resulted coefficient value 0,523. If the Job Satisfaction is one unit, then Performance will increase by 0,523. The coefficient is positive (+) means that there is a positive relationship between

job satisfaction variables (X_2) and the performance variable (Y). With error standard of 0.035 - it means the error rate of Job Satisfaction that Predict Performance is 0.035.

- 4) Regression coefficient X_3 (Organizational Commitment) from multiple linear calculation had coefficient value -0,044. If Organizational Commitment increases by one unit, then Performance will decrease by -0.044. The coefficient is negative (-). It means that there is a positive relationship between the variables of Organizational Commitment (X_3) and performance variable (Y). The error standard is 0.050 - it means that the variable error level of Organizational Commitment that predicts Performance is 0.050.

Test t

Test t is used to figure out how far the influence of independent variables individually to the dependent variable. The testing is executed by using *significance level* 0,05 ($\alpha = 5\%$). If $t_{arithmetic} >$ from t_{table} or significance value $<5\%$ (0.05). It means that H_0 is rejected - there is significant influence between independent variable (Leadership, Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment) on dependent variable (Performance) Partially. Meanwhile, if the significance level of <0.05 and $t < t_{table}$ then (H_1, H_2, H_3 and H_4) is rejected and H_0 accepted. The T-test results can be seen in Table 4.7.

Table 4.7: The Result of T-Test (Partially)

<i>Variable</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>t_{table}</i>	<i>Value significance</i>	<i>Description</i>
Leadership (X1)	10.833	1.974	0.000	Significant
Job Satisfaction (X2)	14.944	1.974	0.000	Significant
Organizational Commitment (X3)	-, 884	1.974	0.378	Not significant

Source: Primary data, 2018

Decision-making according to Sujarweni (2015):

- 1) H_0 is accepted if $t_{arithmetic} < t_{table}$ ($df = n-1$; double-sided (0.025)) and significance value $> 0,05$.
- 2) H_1 is accepted if $t_{count} > t_{table}$ ($df = n-1$, double side (0,025)) and significance value $<0,05$.
- 3) H_2 is accepted if $t_{count} > t_{table}$ ($df = n-1$, double side (0,025)) and significance value $<0,05$.
- 4) H_3 accepted if $t > t_{table}$ ($df = n-1$; the two sides (0.025)) and the significance value <0.05 .
- 5) H_4 is accepted if $t_{count} > t_{table}$ ($df = n-1$, double side (0,025)) and significance value $<0,05$.

t test results in Table 4.7 can be explained as follows:

Hypothesis Test H_1

According to Ghozali (2016), if $t_{counted} > t_{table}$ and significance value <0.05 , it has a significant effect. The results of the t test were value of $t_{counted} 10.833 > t_{table} 1.974$ and leadership variable significance value was $0.000 < 0.05$. These results indicate that leadership has a significant effect on the performance of employees at the RSUD Besuki Situbondo, Indonesia. So H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted.

These results are in line with the studies of Heryanto (2004) and proves that leadership has a positive and significant impact on employee performance. This positive relation shows the influence of leadership on employee performance.

Hypothesis Test H₂

According to Ghozali (2016), if $t_{\text{counted}} > t_{\text{table}}$ and significance value <0.05 , it has a significant effect. The results of the t test was value $t_{\text{counted}} 11.944 > t_{\text{table}} 1.974$, and the value of job satisfaction variable significance was $0.000 < 0.05$. These results indicate that variable of job satisfaction has a significant effect on the performance of employees of RSUD Besuki Situbondo, Indonesia. Then H_0 is rejected and H_2 is accepted. The results are in line with the study that has been done by Devi (2009) which proves that the variable of job satisfaction and motivation shows a significant positive impact on employee performance.

Hypothesis Test H₃

According to Ghozali (2016), if $t_{\text{counted}} > t_{\text{table}}$ and significance value <0.05 , it has a significant effect. The results of the t test showed value $t_{\text{counted}} -0.884 < t_{\text{table}} 1.984$, and the value of variable significance organizational commitment was $0.378 > 0.05$. These results indicate that the organizational commitment variable has no effect on the performance of employees of RSUD Besuki Situbondo, Indonesia. So H_0 is accepted and H_3 is rejected. The results are in line with a study that has been done by Sunarno (2015) which proves that organizational commitment has no effect on the performance of teachers.

Discussion

The Influence of Leadership on Employee Performance RSUD (Public Hospital) Besuki

In table 4.7 t test results has been analyzed by applying partial correlation to figure out the correlation between leadership variables (X_1) and the performance (Y). The test shows significance value = 0,000. This value shows a positive relationship between (X_1) and (Y). The positive meaning here is a direct relationship between leadership variables with performance - It means that if the value of leadership goes up, then the performance will rise significantly. The indicators used in leadership measurement are 8 (eight) indicators that are being fair employee, giving suggestions, supporting the goals achievement, being a catalyst, building secure sense, being a representative of the organization, being a source of inspiration, and being respectful.

Among 8 indicators, (a leader) who always supports the goal achievement of the organization influences employee performance improvement at the best. In addition, respondent has following perceptions: the hospital leader is a highly initiative person in giving excellent idea to improve employee performance. Furthermore, respondents also thought that the leader / director execute a good approach to the employee or to cross-sector to improve the job performance. The leader also supports good ideas / initiatives from employee to build a good organization. For that reason, the leader should always maintain a good atmosphere to improve the employees performance in the public hospital.

The lowest indicator of leadership according to respondents is the source of inspiration. It means that the head of the hospital during this time often look less tidy and less attractive. The appearance of the leader lead to the lack of trust whenever s/he delivers speech. In addition, the respondents explained that the leader also rarely performs a good communication among the employees. This, of course, contributes the low employees performance in the hospital. In other word, applying a good communication principle (good language and politeness) is important for the leader so that the leader becomes a role model in communication for the employee s/he leads.

These results are in line with previous studies by Heryanto (2004) who proved that leadership has a positive and significant impact on employee performance. This positive influence indicates a direct influence between leadership and employee performance, or in other words, a good leadership leads to the high employee performance. Whereas, this significant influence shows that leadership has a significant effect on employee performance.

Influence of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance of RSUD (Public Hospital) Besuki Situbondo, Indonesia

The result of hypothesis test in table 4.7 has been analyzed by applying partial correlation to find out the correlation between job satisfaction variable (X_2) and performance variable (Y). The result shows significance value = 0,000. This value indicates a positive relationship between (X_2) and (Y). The positive meaning here is a direct relationship between job satisfaction variables and employee performance – it means that that if the value of job satisfaction increases then the performance of employees will rise significantly. There are 6 (six) indicators used in the measurement of job satisfaction which are: fair and good service, good communication, work capacity, working environment atmosphere, tools for work performance, and attitude and leadership.

The most influencing indicators on the employee performance is the atmosphere of work environment. The result of the questioner shows that the employee always works based on the job description assigned by the leader and the ability. In addition, the employee thought that the employee feel a pleasure in the work environment and focus the assigned jobs. This pleasant feeling contributed to the employee performance improvement.

The lowest indicator of job satisfaction that can cause the low performance of employees in the hospital according to the respondents obtained is tools that support the implementation of work. In addition, the fairly-distributed services plays role in leading to the low employee performance. Most hospital employees feel that the existing facilities and infrastructure does not meet the standard. This is caused by the newly-established public hospital – RSUD (public hospital) Besuki, Situbondo was built in 2013 so it is still in the process of improving and refining infrastructure. Job satisfaction becomes a sensitive issue for employee. According to the questioner, services distribution among the employee is less fair that the employee feel uncomfortable in performing the job. These results are in line with previous studies by Devi (2009) which proves that the variable of job satisfaction and motivation showed a significant positive effect on employee performance.

Influence of Organizational Commitment on Employee Performance hospitals Besuki Situbondo, Indonesia

Based on the results of hypothesis testing in Table 4.7 can be seen the correlations partially between the variables of organizational commitment (X_3) and a performance variable (Y). The result of the test shows significance value = 0.378. This value shows a negative relationship between (X_3) and (Y). This means that organizational commitment is not proven to affect the performance of employees at RSUD Besuki. There are three (3) indicators used in the measurement of organizational commitment which are: affective commitment (*affective commitment*), continuance commitment (*continuance commitment*), and normative commitment (*normative commitment*).

The result of the questionnaire illustrate that most of the hospital employees have not been able to feel that the hospital is their second home. They cannot feel that the hospital is their own that must be maintained, guarded and strived to be a better hospital in the future. Even, some employees do not feel to loose if there is a better offer in the other workplace.

This is in line with the data of RSUD Besuki RSUD Besuki that the authors observed. The data was about the tilazation of public hospital in 2016 – the data showed that the number of *Bed Occupancy Rate* (BOR) that is the percentage of bed usage in a certain time unit which is only 60.75% (Health Department Standard $> 75\%$), *Average Length Of Stay* (ALOS) is the average length of treatment of a patient 3 days (Health Department Standard 5 - 9 days) while the number of referral of inpatients is about 15.6% (Health Department Standard $< 12\%$).

The reason of those facts is that the status of the employee. The number of respondents whose employment status is probation is about 105 people (61.77%). They are not paid monthly, but they are paid with an uncertaint amount of fee for their services. In addition, the regulation rules the employess that they are not allowed to demand themselves to be a civil servant and demand a monthly salary. Besides, the employees only hire for a year and it is automatically extended if they are needed. The results are in line with previous studies by Sunarno (2015) which proves that organizational commitment is not proven to affect teacher performance.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

Conclusions

Based on the empirical findings, it can be concluded that:

- 1) The result of the hypothesis test proves that leadership variables have a positive and significant impact on employee performance at RSUD Besuki. The calculation of data analysis results significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$. So it can be concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_1 accepted.
- 2) The result of hypothesis test proves that job satisfaction variable has a positive and significant impact on employee performance at RSUD Besuki. The calculation of data analysis results significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$. So it can be concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_2 is accepted.
- 3) The result of hypothesis test proves that organizational commitment variable has no effect on employee performance RSUD Besuki. Calculation result of data analysis results significance value equal to $0,378 > 0,05$. So it can be concluded that H_0 is accepted and H_3 is rejected.

Recommendations

Based on the data, the respondents expect equality and justice for the employee. In the futere, the employee look forwards that The leader does not differentiate one another in the term of job distribution and salary.

A Leader and stake holders of the public hospital is expected to improve the communication among the employees so that the intimacy and togetherness between the leader and employees are built very well. If the leader is able to maintain a family atoshperein the public hospital, s/he will

enhance the employee performance that lead to customer satisfaction. In other words, RSUD Besuki Situbondo, Indonesia is optimally utilized by the surrounding community.

Last, but not least, the researcher expects that employee is able to improve performance, promote professionalism, have professional characteristics that work and provide service in public hospitals whether doctors, nurses, midwives and others. The better performance will lead to customer satisfaction which then might make RSUD Besuki memorable among the patient in terms of goodservice, communication, etc.

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